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Mean grain yield and N use efficiency of irrigated transplanted rice varieties under different SPAD threshold levels, SWMRI farm, Thanjavur (New Cauvery Delta area), Tamil Nadu, India, 1996-98 dry and wet seasons.*

SPAD threshold level/season/variety			Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)			N applied (kg ha ⁻¹)			AEN (kg grain kg ⁻¹ N)		
1996	1997	1998	1996	1997	1998	1996	1997	1998	1996	1997	1998
DS (kuruvai)											
Rice variety: ADT36											
Control	Control	Control	4.1 b	2.8 d	2.7 d	0	0	0	–	–	–
SPAD 29	SPAD 33	SPAD 33	3.7 b	4.2 c	4.0 c	0	30	25	–	45	53
SPAD 31	SPAD 35	SPAD 35	3.8 b	5.3 ab	6.2 b	0	60	45	–	49	80
SPAD 33	SPAD 37	SPAD 37	4.0 b	5.2 b	7.0 a	0	75	85	–	31	51
SPAD 35	SPAD 39	SPAD 39	5.7 a	6.1 a	7.1 a	45	120	110	36	27	41
IR50											
Control	Control	ADT42	3.3 b	3.2 c	2.8 d	0	0	0	–	–	–
SPAD 29	SPAD 33	SPAD 33	3.6 b	5.3 b	4.1 c	0	75	35	–	15	35
SPAD 31	SPAD 35	SPAD 35	3.4 b	6.2 ab	6.6 b	0	75	55	–	26	68
SPAD 33	SPAD 37	SPAD 37	3.5 b	6.0 ab	7.3 a	30	75	75	6	24	60
SPAD 35	SPAD 39	SPAD 39	5.1 a	6.6 a	7.3 a	75	120	125	24	20	36
LSD 0.05			480	467	501						
WS-I (samba)											
W. Ponni	W. Ponni	ASD19									
Control	Control	Control	2.2 d	2.1 d	2.0 d	0	0	0	–	–	–
SPAD 29	SPAD 33	SPAD 33	3.0 c	3.5 bc	3.2 c	50	90	50	17	16	23
SPAD 31	SPAD 35	SPAD 35	3.5 ab	3.8 ab	3.5 c	100	130	70	14	14	21
SPAD 33	SPAD 37	SPAD 37	3.6 ab	3.8 ab	4.1 b	100	140	80	14	13	26
SPAD 35	SPAD 39	SPAD 39	3.9 a	4.3 a	4.1 b	120	160	100	14	14	21
WS-II (thaladi)											
TRY1	TRY1	ADT38									
Control	Control	Control	2.1 d	2.0 d	2.0 d	0	0	0	–	–	–
SPAD 29	SPAD 33	SPAD 33	2.9 c	3.1 c	3.1 c	30	50	50	25	21	22
SPAD 31	SPAD 35	SPAD 35	2.9 c	3.6 b	3.9 bc	80	70	70	10	22	27
SPAD 33	SPAD 37	SPAD 37	3.2 bc	4.0 ab	4.3 b	100	120	100	11	16	23
SPAD 35	SPAD 39	SPAD 39	3.0 bc	4.0 ab	4.8 a	100	130	140	10	15	20
LSD 0.05				558	923	400					

*In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. AEN = additional grain yield over control per kilogram N applied.

On-farm evaluation of chlorophyll meter-based N management in irrigated transplanted rice in the Cauvery Delta, Tamil Nadu, India

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Judicious use of nitrogen (N) fertilizer in rice requires synchronizing N fertilizer applications with plant needs. Predicting plant N requirement through soil testing has not proven valuable for rice because of dynamic changes in native N supply and difficulty in predicting climatic variables that control soil N mineralization and crop growth. The chlorophyll meter is a simple, portable device that accurately measures leaf N status of rice plants *in situ*. It could help improve grain yield and N use efficiency (Peng et al 1996, Balasubramanian et al 1999).

The SPAD-guided N technique was evaluated in farmers' fields in the new and old Cauvery Delta areas of Tamil Nadu, India, during the 1996-98 wet and dry seasons (DS, kuruvai: June to September; WS-I, samba: August to December/January; WS-II, thaladi: October to February). Trials were conducted by TNRRRI and SWMRI to compare grain yield and N use efficiency of irrigated transplanted rice under different N management practices. Three N treatments—zero-N control, local N recommendation, and SPAD-guided N—were

evaluated in the 1996-97 trials. A fourth treatment of SPAD-guided N with a basal application of 20 kg N ha⁻¹ was included in the 1997-98 trials. Each farm had one replication in the old area and two in the new area.

Soils of the experimental fields in the new Cauvery Delta belong to two series—Madukkhur (Alfisol) and Pattukkottai (Alfisol)—while those of the old Cauvery Delta constitute three major series—Kalathur (Udorthentic Chromustert), Adanur (Entic Chromustert), and Padugai (Typic

Table 1. Total N applied, grain yield, and N use efficiency of irrigated transplanted rice under different N management practices in the new Cauvery Delta area of Tamil Nadu, India, 1996-98 cropping seasons.^a

Treatment	DS (kuruvai)			WS-I (samba) ^b			WS-II (thaladi)		
	N applied (kg ha ⁻¹)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	AEN ^c	N applied (kg ha ⁻¹)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	AEN	N applied (kg ha ⁻¹)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	AEN
<i>1996-97</i>		2 farms (2 reps each)		7 farms (2 reps each)			3 farms (2 reps each)		
Control	0	5.3 b	–	0	3.4 b	–	0	3.4 b	–
Local N recommendation	125 (3)	6.4 a	8.8	150 (4)	4.8 a	9.7	150 (4)	5.1 a	11.7
SPAD-based N	60 (2)	7.1 a	29.0	56 (2)	4.6 a	20.7	60 (2)	5.1 a	32.0
<i>1997-98</i>		6 farms (2 reps each)		3 farms (2 reps each)			3 farms (2 reps each)		
Control	0	2.9 b	–	0	2.7 b	–	0	2.5 b	–
Local N recommendation	125 (3)	3.9 a	7.6	150 (4)	3.8 a	7.3	150 (4)	3.4 a	5.6
SPAD-based N	75 (3)	4.1 a	13.5	72 (3)	3.5 a	11.3	55 (2)	3.1 a	10.6
Basal + SPAD-N	107 (4)	4.4 a	15.9	92 (4)	3.4 a	8.0	65 (3)	3.0 a	6.4

^aAll treatments received 22-42-10 kg ha⁻¹ of P, K, and Zn in the dry season and 26-50-10 kg ha⁻¹ of P, K, and Zn in the wet season. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. Number in parentheses refers to number of split N applications. ^bFlood affected yields during 1997-98. ^cAEN = additional grain yield over control per kilogram N applied.

Ustifluent). The number of on-farm trials conducted during each season is given in Tables 1 and 2.

In SPAD-guided N treatments, leaf N status was monitored weekly starting from 14 d after transplanting (DAT) until first flowering. Measurements were obtained from the youngest fully expanded leaf of 10 randomly selected plants from each plot. Whenever the average SPAD reading fell below the critical value of 35, N fertilizer was applied immediately. During the DS, the amount of N applied each time was 30 kg N ha⁻¹ from early to maximum tillering stage (14–28 DAT), 45 kg N ha⁻¹ from maximum tillering to panicle initiation (PI) stage (29–48 DAT), and 30 kg N ha⁻¹ from PI to flowering (49 DAT to flowering); it was reduced to 20-30-20 kg N ha⁻¹ for corresponding stages in the WS. All treatments received a basal application of 22-40-10 kg ha⁻¹ of phosphorus (P), potassium (K), and zinc (Zn) in the DS and 26-50-10 kg ha⁻¹ of P, K, and Zn in the WS. Zinc was applied only to Zn-deficient soils.

Grain yield was determined from three 5-m² sample areas from each plot at 14% moisture content. The agronomic efficiency of applied N (AEN) was calculated as additional grain yield over the control per kilogram N applied.

Trial results indicated no significant differences in crop response to N treat-

Table 2. Total N applied, grain yield, and N use efficiency of irrigated transplanted rice under different N management practices in the old Cauvery Delta area of Tamil Nadu, India, 1996-98.^a

Treatment	N applied (kg ha ⁻¹)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	AEN ^b
<i>1996-98 dry season^c</i>			
1996 DS (mean of 5 farms)			
Control	0	5.1 c	–
Local N recommendation	125 (3)	5.8 b	5.3
SPAD-35 N	105 (3)	6.7 a	14.6
1997 DS (mean of 12 farms)			
Control	0	4.9 c	–
Local N recommendation	125 (3)	7.1 b	21.5
SPAD-35 N	67 (2)	8.3 a	50.5
Basal + SPAD-35 N	88 (3)	7.7 a	31.9
1998 DS (mean of 7 farms)			
Control	0	4.0 b	–
Local N recommendation	125 (3)	6.1 a	16.5
SPAD-35 N	61 (2)	6.1 a	36.4
Basal + SPAD-35 N	67 (3)	5.8 a	27.3
<i>1997-98 wet season^d</i>			
WS-I: samba (mean of 9 farms)			
Control	0	4.3 b	–
Local N recommendation	150 (4)	7.4 b	20.9
SPAD-N	69 (3)	7.4 a	45.2
Basal + SPAD-N	89 (4)	7.3 a	33.7
WS-II: thaladi (mean of 6 farms)			
Control	0	3.4 c	–
Local N recommendation	150 (4)	5.5 ab	13.9
SPAD-N	70 (3)	5.7 a	32.1
Basal + SPAD-N	90 (4)	5.4 ab	21.7

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. Number in parentheses refers to number of split N applications. ^bAEN = additional grain yield over control per kilogram N applied. ^cAll treatments received 22-42-10 kg ha⁻¹ of P, K, and Zn. ^dAll treatments received 26-50-10 kg ha⁻¹ of P, K, and Zn.

ments in various soil series in both zones; hence, data across soil series were pooled for analysis and interpretation. In farms of the new Cauvery Delta, grain yields were generally higher for all seasons in 1996-97 than in 1997-98 (Table 1) due to heavy rain-

fall and flooding at critical crop growth stages in 1997-98. In both good and bad years, the SPAD-guided N treatment recorded a significantly higher grain yield than the control, but it was on a par with the local N recommendation in all three cropping seasons. The AEN values of the SPAD treatment were 1.5–2.5 times that of the local N recommendation (Table 1). Savings in fertilizer rates of 50–65 kg N ha⁻¹ were recorded during the DS; 78–95 kg N ha⁻¹ were saved during the WS. Data also indicated that no basal N application is required for the SPAD method in soils of the new Cauvery Delta because there was no substantial increase in grain yield with a basal application of 20 kg N ha⁻¹.

In farms of the old Cauvery Delta, the crop response to different N

treatments was similar to that observed in the new Cauvery Delta (Table 2). Likewise, AEN values followed the same trend. Grain yield was highest for the SPAD method, but it was on a par with the local N recommendation and SPAD method with a basal application of 20 kg N ha⁻¹. The data again indicated that basal N application is not advantageous for various soil types in the old Cauvery Delta. An average savings of 80 kg ha⁻¹ for N fertilizer was obtained in both the DS and WS.

These results clearly demonstrated the advantage of using the chlorophyll meter technique to fine-tune N recommendations for various seasons in the Cauvery Delta. There is a potential to save 50–95 kg N ha⁻¹ if refined N recommendations are used. This study focused on using a

single SPAD threshold value to assess N needs of rice crops. Further research is ongoing to determine the effect of using a range of SPAD values (e.g., 32–34, 35–37, 38–40, etc.) for synchronizing N application with crop demand in rice.

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Efficiency of controlled-release urea and coated urea fertilizers in irrigated transplanted rice in Andhra Pradesh, India

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Nitrogen (N) is one of the major nutrients applied to rice. The recovery of N from N applied to wetland rice, however, seldom exceeds 40% (De Datta and Buresh 1989). Thus, new methods or strategies are needed to improve the agronomic and economic efficiency of N fertilizers in rice that would also minimize fertilizer-related environmental pollution. Some of the promising N management techniques include split application, subsurface placement, and the use of slow-release and coated urea fertilizers (Mohanty et al 1999).

We evaluated the relative efficiency of selected controlled-release urea (CRU) and coated urea fertilizers compared with a single basal application of prilled urea on irrigated transplanted rice (cv Ajaya) at the DRR farm, Andhra Pradesh, India. Field trials were conducted during the monsoon (kharif: July to October 1997) and winter

(rabi: November 1997 to March 1998) seasons on a typical Vertisol soil (pH in water 8.3, cation exchange capacity (CEC) 45 cmol P⁺ kg⁻¹, organic carbon 5.5 g kg⁻¹, available KMnO₄-extractable N 150 kg ha⁻¹, Olsen P 30.4 kg ha⁻¹, and NH₄Ac-extractable K 244.5 kg ha⁻¹). Treatments were four types of fertilizer N and a no-N control (Table 1) arranged in a randomized complete block design with three replications.

Types of fertilizer N used were CRU with 4.5% and 6% coating, gypsum-coated urea (GCU), neem-coated urea (NCU), and commonly available prilled urea (PU). CRU, a free-flowing granular fertilizer coated with polyurethane and wax, had 43% N, 1.3% biuret, 120 ppm free ammonia, 0.08% moisture, and 1.8% conditioner. All fertilizers were broadcast in a single dose of 86 kg N ha⁻¹ just before

planting. Phosphorus (P) as single superphosphate and potassium (K) as muriate of potash were applied to all plots at locally recommended rates of 27 kg P and 32 kg K ha⁻¹.

Among different fertilizers, CRU 6% produced the highest grain yields, whereas a single basal application of PU had the lowest yields in both seasons (Table 1). Grain yields obtained with CRU 6% were 38% and 27% higher than those obtained with PU in the monsoon and winter seasons, respectively. In the monsoon season, yield of CRU 6% was significantly higher than that of CRU 4.5%, but, during winter, there was no significant difference in grain yield of the two CRU fertilizers. Grain yields produced by GCU and NCU were similar but significantly lower than those of the two CRUs in the monsoon season. During the winter season, how-